

QUALITY CONTROL AND STANDARDIZATION OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS IN THE DRY EXTRACT 'EXTRADENT'

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Relevance: Herbal preparations remain an important direction in pharmaceutical science due to their wide pharmacological effects and relatively low toxicity. 'Extradent' is a dry extract consisting of *Calendula officinalis*, *Urtica dioica*, *Capsella bursa-pastoris*, and *Polygonum hydropiper*. These plants are known to contain flavonoids, carotenoids, tannins, amino acids, and mineral elements that contribute to the therapeutic properties of the preparation.

Keywords: Extradent, quality control, standardization, rutin, flavonoids, HPLC, UV-spectrophotometry, carotenoids, tannins, amino acids, minerals.

Purpose of the research. To ensure quality control and standardization of the dry extract 'Extradent' by identifying its main biologically active substances, with special attention to flavonoids.

Methods. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and UV-spectrophotometry were applied. The extract was dissolved in 70% ethanol and filtered. Chromatographic analysis was carried out on a C18 column with acetonitrile, water, and acetic acid as the mobile phase. UV-spectrophotometry was used to measure the total flavonoid content using the $AlCl_3$ complex method.

Results . The chromatogram revealed several phenolic compounds, with rutin identified as the main marker. Its clear peak confirmed its suitability for standardization. Spectrophotometric analysis showed a significant presence of flavonoids beyond rutin, indicating the complex composition of the extract. Literature data confirm that carotenoids, tannins, amino acids, and minerals also strengthen the therapeutic potential of 'Extradent'.

Conclusion. The combination of HPLC and UV-spectrophotometry is an effective approach for the quality control of 'Extradent'. Rutin can be used as a reliable marker, while the presence of other biologically active compounds ensures a wide spectrum of pharmacological activity. The results provide a basis for certification and broader medical application of the preparation.